

Wetlands and Global Climate Change: A Critical Review

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Abstract Wetlands are important ecosystems that provide goods and services of critical importance to human societies. Wetlands cover 6% of the world land surface and store the largest share i.e., 12% of the global carbon pool. Global climate change is recognized as threat to wetlands. The raise temperature, Carbon dioxide levels and change in precipitation region to cause significant changes in productivity, biodiversity and nutrient turnover, scenic beauty, ecotourism, economic and mental health benefits of the Wetlands. This review is presented with the view of explore strategies for the planning to mitigate the likely cause of climate change and sustainable management strategy for wetlands.

Keywords Wetlands, Climate Change, Biodiversity, Goods and Services.

Introduction

Wetlands are the land in transition between terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems where the water table is usually at or near or above the surface of lands covered by shallow water¹⁸. Wetlands globally encloses 6% of the world land area and contain about 12% global carbon pool playing an important role in global cycle^{9,12}. Wetlands "Kidney of earth" provide diverse ecosystem goods and services. For human beings^{1,7,8,23}. Wetland of many ecosystem services to humankind, such as food, shelter, water purification, sediment retention, groundwater recharge, climate mitigation, nutrient cycling, wildlife protection recreation, scenic beauty and spiritual activities^{3,11,17,20}.

Objective of study This review paper aims to access the possible responses of a wetland ecosystem to climate change

Review of Literature

In recent years, wetlands have been outstandingly affected by human activities and climate change¹⁹. Wetland have become one most threatened habitat of the world facing degradation due to expanding human population, Urban and industrial expansion, fossil fuel burning, deforestation, land use change, pollution and climate change^{13,16}. Climate change is recognized as a measure of threat to the survival of species and integrity of ecosystems worldwide. The number of rainy days and total amount of precipitation have decreased due to increase in concentration of greenhouse gasses². Decreases precipitation will create problem associated with already going demand for water and hence alter the freshwater flow of wetland⁷, whereas rise temperature can aggregate the Problem of eutrophication, loading of algal bloom, fish leads and dead zones in the surface water¹⁰. This proposes a fundamental and acute demand to determine how to shape future wetland restoration initiatives in light of global climate change.

Analysis

(i) Provisioning services and climate extremes

Provisioning services are the production services that reflect the goods and services produced in the ecosystem. These include provision of food, fish production, wild life, fresh water, fuel, genetic resources and medicines^{5,19,21}. Raising temperature tends coupled with the reduction in rainfall frequency and intensity can profound effect on wetlands²². The water is limited in different parts of the world due to climate change and rising demands of people¹⁴. Pressures on wetlands are probable to be arbitrate through change in hydrology direct and indirect effects of changes in temperature as well as land use change^{4,9}. The climate Change in the future dry years is expected to induce shortage in the availability of surface and groundwater recharge¹⁹. During the time of high rainfall, the reservoirs may overflow (producing flood events) and can cause damage to the human and natural system⁷.

(ii) Regulatory services and climate extremes

Regulatory services are defined as the benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes¹. Climate change is recognized as a major threat to regulatory services, such as greenhouse gasses, altering the local and regional temperature precipitation regulation, water hydrology excess of nutrients and pollutants removal sediments retention, control floods and habitat for pollinators^{5,15,18,19}.

(iii) Cultural Services and climate extremes

Cultural services relate to service people obtain from the ecosystem through recreation, enrichment, beauty, spiritual, reflection and aesthetic values^{5,6,16}. The increase in the frequency and intensity of climatic disasters such as floods, heat waves, drought results the degradation of wetlands reducing their scenic beauty, ecotourism and health benefits¹.

These climatic extremes also lead to loss of jobs and rural livelihood affecting communities physical, mental and economic health⁷.

Conclusion

Wetlands are the most useful and important ecosystem for the welfare of human societies for their services. Due to rising global temperature, changes in precipitation regime and elevated carbon dioxide will affect the goods and services of Wetlands. We can do this by pledging wetland refurbishment programs and implementing sustainable ecosystem management plans now as we continue to work on the task of reducing CO₂ emission and reversing existing climate change trends.

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